

How to communicate science in times of crisis?

A friendly guide for journalists

COALESCE

Co-creating the EU Competence Centre for
Science Communication

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index

Definitions to begin with: crisis, complexity, uncertainty and risk	4
<hr/>	
Pre-crisis. Getting prepared	8
<hr/>	
Imminent crisis. Starting off on the right foot	11
<hr/>	
Crisis in real time. The roller coaster of science communication	14
<hr/>	
Post crisis. Follow-up and reflective practices	18
<hr/>	
How to find help at the European Competence Centre for Science Communication	22

Earthquakes, wildfires, droughts, floods, and other natural disasters, along with the social impacts of AI and other emerging technologies, are no longer the exclusive domain of science reporters. In times of crisis, all journalists, including those not specialised in science and technology, are called to report quickly and accurately, often under pressure and with limited access to verified information.

The way journalists frame a story, the experts they choose to interview, and the messages they highlight can significantly influence how the public understands a crisis and how they respond to it.

Communicating during emergencies presents several challenges. One of the first is grasping the complexity of the scientific knowledge involved, starting with the meaning of “risk” in scientific terms, which often differs from its everyday use. Journalists also need to understand the multiple interests and perspectives at stake and be able to navigate them carefully and ethically. Another key challenge is identifying and giving voice to a diverse range of credible, independent experts while avoiding those with hidden agendas or conflicts of interest.

At the same time, journalists must deal with the intense emotions of affected communities and audiences, as well as the political dimension of the crisis, which increasingly includes polarisation, disinformation, and widespread distrust toward anything that is not openly aligned with a particular position.

All of this becomes even more complex when reporters face constraints within their newsrooms or work as freelancers, with limited institutional support and scarce resources.

This guide does not aim to solve the structural difficulties of the profession. However, it offers a set of reflections and practical suggestions to help journalists of any background approach science communication in times of crisis more effectively.

In the final section, you will also find suggestions on seeking support from the European Competence Centre for Science Communication, powered by the COALESCE project.

01

Definitions to begin with: crisis, complexity, uncertainty and risk

Crisis

A crisis is a broad, often prolonged situation that causes significant disruption and involves complex challenges that cannot be solved immediately. It may **develop gradually** or **emerge from a poorly managed** emergency. In contrast, an **emergency** is an immediate, often sudden event that poses a direct threat to life, health, the environment, or property. Earthquakes, volcanic eruptions, or tornadoes are all emergencies, varying in scale and impact, that require urgent response.

If managed effectively, emergencies can be mitigated or resolved before they escalate, and international efforts, such as the Early Warnings for All¹, are being made towards reinforcing coordinated early warning systems. However, **without proper response** and coordination, an emergency can evolve into a **full-blown crisis** with long-term consequences.

In an emergency, journalists are among the first to be **actively involved**. Their role is critical: helping the public **understand** what is happening, providing **clear and timely information**, and acting as a **dissemination and communication bridge** between institutions and citizens. However, their work goes beyond the immediate moment. The way journalists cover emer-

1) <https://wmo.int/activities/early-warnings-all>

gencies can shape how future crises are **perceived, understood,** and **managed,** both by decision-makers and by the public.

Climate change is a clear example of a **long-term issue** that affects multiple sectors of the economy and society. Yet, it was only widely recognised as a crisis once its impacts **became tangible and visible** to the broader public.

In the face of both emergencies and crises, people seek clear, reliable, and unambiguous information. But **such clarity** is not always possible. Many of the problems involved are highly complex, their evolution is difficult to predict, and the science behind them is inherently uncertain.

Science can help **analyse and assess risks,** but it cannot offer definitive answers or eliminate uncertainty.

For **journalists,** this presents a significant communication challenge: translating complex, evolving scientific knowledge into understandable information, without oversimplifying or offering false reassurance. For **audiences,** it often means confronting difficult truths, accepting ambiguity, and navigating decisions without clear-cut answers.

Complexity and uncertainty

The term **complexity** refers to the intricate and interconnected nature of many issues, where multiple factors interact in ways that are difficult to predict or fully understand. Science is inherently complex and uncertain since **scientific knowledge** is constantly evolving, always partial, and open to refinement. There is always something we know, and something still to be explored or clarified.

Crises often amplify this **uncertainty**. They tend to unfold across **multiple domains** (social, economic, environmental and geopolitical) over an extended period of time, and involve incomplete or rapidly changing information. This lack of clarity is often due to the **very nature** of the phenomenon, leading to a certain degree of **unpredictability**, and even scientists and other experts cannot foresee every outcome.

This does not mean that science is unreliable or should be mistrusted. On the contrary, **science remains the most robust and reliable method** we have for understanding and responding to complexity and uncertainty. Especially during a crisis, the scientific approach, grounded in evidence, rigorous methodology, and open inquiry, offers a **structured way** to make sense of what is happening. It helps collect data, **test hypotheses**, and **refine understanding** as new evidence emerges.

Unlike opinions or unchecked claims, science relies on peer review, reproducibility, integrity and transparency. These core principles help **minimise bias and error**.

Risk

Uncertainty does not mean that nothing can be said. Science cannot always provide exact predictions, but it can **estimate the probability** that something might happen, and this can and should be communicated. A clear example is hurricanes: meteorologists cannot predict with certainty whether a storm will hit a specific location, but they can **forecast its likely path, intensity, and timing** based on models and available data. This allows authorities to **issue warnings** and gives people time to prepare, evacuate if needed, and reduce the impact.

Crisis management must go hand in hand with **risk communication**. Authorities and experts have a responsibility to share available information with affected communities in an **open and transparent way**, enabling people to make informed decisions.

Understanding risk requires a fundamental distinction: **risk** is not the same as **hazard**. A hazard is a phenomenon that can potentially cause harm, such as a hurricane, flood, or toxic spill. Hazards vary in magnitude depending on the **potential consequences**: how many people are exposed, how intense the impact may be, and how long-lasting the effects.

But risk also depends on **probability**. Two areas might face the same hazard, but if one is hit by major storms every five years and the other every fifty, the risk is clearly different. Similarly, a hurricane making landfall in a **densely populated coastal city** carries a much higher risk than the same storm hitting an **uninhabited stretch of shoreline**.

In short, hazards of the same magnitude do not always pose the same level of risk.

Estimating risk relies on data: historical records, environmental monitoring, exposure levels, and vulnerability of people and infrastructure. When data is **scarce or incomplete**, risk estimates become **less accurate**. This is an essential aspect for journalists to communicate clearly during a crisis, helping audiences understand both what is known and what remains uncertain.

02

Pre-crisis. Getting prepared

A good address book and network

Crises will always occur, sometimes as sudden emergencies that severely impact communities in a short time, other times as long-term challenges that gradually escalate into major societal risks. What journalists **do between crises** is just as important as what they **do during them**. Periods of **relative calm** offer a crucial opportunity to prepare for future emergencies.

One of the most valuable tools a journalist can have is a **well-curated address book**. The **fragmentation and specialisation** of scientific knowledge means that even scientists themselves rarely have a complete view of all the disciplines relevant to a given crisis. For journalists, keeping up with fast-moving scientific developments is even more challenging.

That's why it's essential to build relationships with a broad and well-chosen network of experts. Finding the right expert for the right question, someone with the appropriate specialisation and communication skills, is key to producing accurate and trustworthy reporting. To support this effort, the European Competence Centre for Science Communication virtual platform integrates an **online matchmaking tool** to help journalists identify suitable experts, organisations and build a broad network.

A good address book is not just a list of individual names, nor should it be. Science is not an **individual endeavour**: knowledge is **produced collectively**, within research institutes, universities, governmental and inter-governmental organisations. These institutions are essential sources of specialised, evidence-based information, and can help journalists navigate complex topics more accurately. Rather than relying solely on well-known or media-friendly scientists, journalists should also make use of **institutional press offices**. These communication teams can help identify the **most suitable experts** for a given topic, individuals with the relevant expertise, the most current research, and the ability to explain it clearly. This approach might help **avoid overexposure** of a few high-profile figures and contribute to **more diverse, gender balanced and reliable** reporting.

It's also important to remember that **experts are not neutral** players. They are affiliated with institutions, research centres, or private companies; they rely on public or private funding; and many benefit from public visibility. In short, experts are also stakeholders, and like any other, they may have **interests** that influence their perspective.

Journalists should approach scientists with the same combination of respect and critical distance they apply to any other source. Expertise deserves recognition, but it should never be exempt from scrutiny. Potential **conflicts of interest**, such as institutional affiliations or funding ties, are not necessarily signs of bad faith, but they should be **identified, verified**, and clearly **disclosed** when relevant.

Practising **due diligence** with scientific sources, such as asking questions, checking backgrounds, and being transparent, enables audiences to assess the information critically and in context. This approach not only reinforces the **credibility** of journalism, but also **strengthens public trust** in science.

Giving voice to differences, building trust

No one is truly neutral, and journalism should be transparent about that. But being transparent doesn't mean amplifying conflict or fuelling distrust. On the contrary, responsible journalism involves **acknowledging different positions** without turning them into **opposite fronts**. This is especially important when it comes to experts and research institutions, as **undermining trust in them** can ultimately harm the very communities journalists aim to inform.

Journalists have the power and the duty to open spaces for dialogue between researchers, policymakers, and citizens, where different priorities, values, and viewpoints can be heard and understood. By giving **voice to these differences** early on, journalism can help **reduce the risk of polarisation** and social tension when emergencies occur.

Dialogical formats like public debates, citizen panels, or call-in radio shows, can support mutual understanding. They allow people to make sense of complex situations together and to reflect on the knowledge available. Communication in a crisis is not only about conveying urgent facts. It's also about cultivating **a shared ground** for collective response. Participatory and dialogical formats help **reinforce democratic values** and serve as an **antidote** to the increasingly polarised and aggressive tone of global public discourse.

When **trust is nurtured in advance**, scientists and experts are more willing to engage with journalists during a crisis, aware of the crucial role of accurate, independent public communication. Conversely, improvised or careless communication can harm both the relationship with experts—many of whom are wary of how scientific issues are handled by the media—and the public's access to clear, reliable information in the most critical moments.

03

Imminent crisis. Starting off on the right foot

Not all stories are good stories: framing and its consequences

How a crisis is narrated, the words and expressions used, the tone adopted, the metaphors chosen, shapes how audiences interpret and respond to it. This process is known as **framing**, and it plays a central role in **sense-making**, or how people understand what is happening around them. Some frames help clarify complexity and encourage constructive action; others may distort reality, trigger fear, or shut down public engagement. Journalists must be mindful of the frames they adopt and ready to question, adjust, or reject frames proposed by others when those narratives **risk reinforcing misunderstanding or causing harm**.

Huge care must be taken in the language used during crises. Terms like “crisis,” “emergency,” and “urgent” are sometimes **necessary** to convey the seriousness of a situation, but when overused, they can **backfire**. Repeated **alarmist language** can desensitise the public or provoke panic and irrational decisions. Worse, such framing may **obscure underlying causes**, like structural inequality or political neglect, that made the situation so severe in the first place.

A striking example of problematic framing in **environmental reporting** is the frequent use of **apocalyptic language**: phrases like “the planet is dying,” “irreversible collapse,” or “the end of the world.” While these expres-

sions aim to **convey urgency**, they often **overwhelm audiences** and can lead to **disengagement or fatalism**. When people are told that disaster is inevitable, many feel powerless and stop paying attention: “If it’s already too late, what’s the point?” Others may turn to **denial**, suspecting manipulation or exaggeration. Moreover, this kind of framing can contribute to **emotional burnout or eco-anxiety**, especially among younger generations. It’s essential to report the gravity of environmental threats, but equally important to focus on constructive approaches, **highlight possible responses, collective agency**, and stories of adaptation and resilience. Urgency without hope risks silencing the very action it seeks to inspire.

Another classic example is the framing of **medical research** as a “war,” such as the “war on cancer.” While it may sound powerful, this metaphor sets **unrealistic expectations**: it implies a final battle and total victory, when in fact, cancer is a diverse group of diseases, affecting individuals in very different ways. Research is making steady progress, enabling many people to live longer and better lives, even when complete remission is impossible. Framing cancer as a war can lead to **frustration, fear**, or the **false belief** that science is failing, when the opposite is true.

These examples show how **specific frames can distort complex realities** or lead to emotional fatigue, confusion, or disengagement. Journalists should be aware that the way they tell a story can influence not just how people feel, but also what they think they can do. Whenever possible, reporting should **make space for informed action**, not just alarm. Helping audiences understand where they stand and what is at stake is essential, but so is giving them a sense that **responses** are possible, that **solutions** exist, and that individuals, institutions and communities have a **role to play**.

The political dimension

When a crisis has **strong political dimensions**, public debate often ends up obscuring the scientific and technological complexity of the issue, its interpretation, possible solutions, and the policymaking that follows. **Political polarisation** can reduce nuanced, evidence-based discussions to binary oppositions. This was clearly seen during the COVID-19 pandemic, with fierce debates over mask-wearing, vaccines, and lockdowns. The result is a **harsh, polarised**, and often **unproductive** conversation.

Journalists have the **responsibility** to investigate and report on the political dynamics of a crisis. But they also have a **crucial role** in making the **scientific dimension** visible. This means clearly explaining what the scientific community knows, how that knowledge is produced, and what degree of certainty or uncertainty surrounds it. Especially in fast-evolving situations where knowledge is still being built, as in the case of COVID, journalism helps the public distinguish between **what is established and what is still under debate**.

Public institutions are **not always ready**, or willing, to communicate uncertainty. In some cases, they may avoid acknowledging it for fear of losing authority. In others, their communication may be shaped or constrained by political pressures. This makes journalism even more essential. Journalists must be able to **highlight contradictions**, clarify what information is based on solid evidence, and explain what remains unknown or uncertain. Doing so helps preserve the **distinction between science and politics**, giving the public the tools to understand both.

04

Crisis in real time. The roller coaster of science communication

Values and emotions

In times of crisis or when addressing urgent societal challenges, **values and emotions** play a central role. All stakeholders, including scientists, journalists and institutions, should be aware of their own emotional responses and those of others, and should consider them thoughtfully when communicating. Among professionals, journalists are often the most skilled at **reading public sentiment**, and they play a crucial role in setting the tone of the wider conversation around a crisis.

Emotions are not only inevitable. They are informative. They can reveal the underlying **values at stake** and help explain the intensity of public concern. Giving space to emotions and values in communication can make it more relatable and compelling, enabling journalists to connect with audiences and, in some cases, to prompt action.

At the same time, journalists must **strike a balance**: using emotion to convey meaning and urgency, without contributing to the **noise** of the **infodemic** or allowing emotional framing to drown out facts and evidence. One emotion that deserves special attention is **trust**: who is trusted, by whom, and why? And to what extent can journalists play a role in helping the public trust those who are worthy of that trust?

Authorities, ambassadors, role models and influencers

During a crisis, distinguishing between **competence and authority** becomes essential. Authority may be institutional, granted by governments, universities, or research bodies, while competence is linked to knowledge and expertise. The two do not always coincide. Fame and trust don't necessarily go hand in hand either.

The COVID-19 pandemic offered clear examples of this dynamic. Some scientists became **media stars**, frequently invited to comment well beyond their area of expertise. At the same time, public figures and **influencers** without a scientific background gained visibility as supposed authorities on complex health and policy issues. Meanwhile, anecdotal information circulating through personal networks (typically "a friend of a friend said..."), often proved **more influential** than **official channels**, especially among certain social groups. This highlights **one of the central principles** of crisis communication: trust tends to **follow proximity**. The closer a source feels to us, the more likely we are to believe it.

For these reasons, journalists must be especially careful when choosing which public figures to platform. It's essential to **avoid promoting incompetence** just because someone is visible or relatable. A good understanding of who is reliable in a given domain makes it easier to identify **appropriate ambassadors**, people who can translate complex knowledge accurately and responsibly.

At the same time, journalists should avoid turning **competent experts** into **general-purpose** media personalities. When scientists comment on everything, from epidemiology to education policy to geopolitics, they risk **blurring the boundaries** of their own authority. This ultimately weakens public understanding of how science works and what it can (and cannot) deliver.

Disinformation, misinformation and fake news

Crises are fertile ground for the spread of false or misleading information. The term “fake news” is often used broadly, but it covers a wide range of content and intent. **Misinformation** refers to incorrect information shared without malicious intent, often due to error or misunderstanding. **Disinformation** is false information deliberately created to deceive.

Addressing these phenomena is complex. The **speed of sharing** on digital platforms, the emotional responses triggered by crises, and the **low visibility of reliable sources** all contribute to spreading false content. While misinformation has always existed, social media amplifies its reach and impact exponentially.

Clickbait headlines and **sensationalist** content further **distort** the landscape, and media outlets themselves are not immune. In the race for visibility and engagement, some outlets **prioritise traffic over accuracy**, especially during emergencies, when emotions are heightened and fear spreads quickly. Journalists must be aware that clickbait and **unverified claims** are **particularly dangerous** in times of crisis, as they can fuel confusion, panic, or denial, ultimately complicating crisis response.

In recent years, **generative AI** has emerged as a **new source of risk**. Although AI-generated disinformation is still a tiny fraction of total false content detected in the EU, **its growth is significant**. Fake images, videos, audio, and text generated by AI tools now circulate widely, especially during sensitive events like conflicts, disasters, or elections. Journalists must **stay ahead of this trend**, developing both **awareness** and **technical capacity** to verify content and avoid amplification.

Fortunately, there are **growing resources** to support this effort. **Fact-checking** platforms and **verification tools** can help assess the reliability of content, trace its origins, and evaluate supporting data. More importantly, journalists can shift **from debunking to prebunking**: proactively identifying and exposing manipulative narratives before they gain traction.

The false balance

One of the most problematic and misleading journalistic practices, especially in science and crisis reporting, is the so-called **false balance**. This occurs when two opposing views are presented as **equally credible**, even when **most evidence supports only one side**. While the principle of listening to all sides is a cornerstone of journalistic ethics and deontology, applying it without context can do more harm than good.

In cases like climate change, vaccine safety, or the origin of a virus, false balance gives undue visibility to fringe or unsubstantiated opinions, making an issue appear far more **controversial** than it actually is. This distorts public understanding and creates confusion at a time when clarity is crucial. The result is a false sense of debate where there is, in fact, a strong scientific consensus.

False balance is **harmful** because it **misrepresents reality** and prevents audiences from accessing clear, evidence-based information. In moments of crisis, this can **slow down public response**, undermine trust in institutions, and deepen divisions. Instead of aiming for artificial symmetry, journalists should focus on the **weight of evidence**, reflecting the state of **scientific consensus** while still acknowledging genuine uncertainty or minority views without exaggerating their significance.

False balance persists in part because **controversy sells**. Polarised debates attract attention, drive clicks, and create the impression of an active, engaged media space. However, short-term visibility is not the same as **long-term credibility**. Media outlets and journalists who stay faithful to their core mission, which is serving the **public interest** with accurate, honest reporting, may not be immediately rewarded in terms of audience metrics, but over time, they are more likely to be seen as trustworthy, independent, and worthy of support. This relationship of trust between credible media and their audience can thus become a **foundation for financial sustainability**. Readers, listeners or viewers who recognise the value and reliability of a news source are more likely to support it, sometimes directly, through subscriptions, donations, or memberships. In this sense, **credibility** is not just a journalistic principle, but also a **long-term investment**.

05

Post crisis. Follow-up and reflective practices

Reporting the end of a crisis

When an emergency fades from the headlines, it often disappears from public discourse, yet **its consequences** are far from over. The aftermath and long-term effects of a crisis can be just **as significant as the event** itself. Health emergencies, environmental disasters, and social conflicts **rarely end** with the resolution of the immediate problem. They leave behind consequences that affect communities, policies, economies, and institutions.

Journalists have a **responsibility to follow up**. Continuing to cover a crisis after its peak allows for a more measured, **in-depth approach** that fosters better **public understanding** and **greater preparedness** for the future. It also helps the audience grasp the **full scope** of the story: how recovery is progressing, what lessons have been learned, and how people and systems are adapting.

Long-term reporting is also a way to **hold institutions accountable**. Following up on promises made during a crisis, whether by national or local governments, international organisations, or private actors, is a key to ensuring **transparency and public trust**. Investigating whether those commitments have been met is not just the domain of investigative journalism: it is a necessary function of journalism in the public interest.

In addition, **sustained coverage** can challenge the perception that each emergency is an isolated event. Many crises are part of **broader systemic**

problems: climate disasters, for example, are often linked to ongoing environmental degradation. By connecting these dots, journalists help communities understand risks in context, anticipate future emergencies, and **demand long-term solutions.**

Reflecting on successes and failures

The period after a crisis can also offer a valuable **opportunity for reflection:** on what worked, what didn't, and how communication could be improved next time. In some science communication fields, such as museums or science centres, **reflective practice** is an established tool. Thanks to the **data collected in evaluation studies,** but also based on **informal observations,** staff regularly assess the effectiveness of exhibitions or programmes. These insights are then used to refine future initiatives and better meet audience needs.

While journalism has not traditionally embraced this kind of structured reflection, today's media are increasingly driven by **data and engagement metrics.** Audience feedback, beyond clicks, views, and shares, is becoming a crucial asset, particularly for media outlets that rely on subscriptions, memberships, or donations. In these models, long-term trust and meaningful relationships with readers are key to survival.

Engagement is becoming **key in journalism,** particularly for those media that rely more and more on their audiences for their economic survival, such as those whose business model is strongly based on **subscription, membership, readers' donation** and other income streams.

But real engagement is not about viral content or attention spikes. It means cultivating an **ongoing dialogue** with the public, through newsletters, surveys, community events, live interactions on social media, or subscriber-only spaces. A newsroom that **knows its audience and listens regularly** is far better positioned to respond effectively in times of crisis. It can adjust its language, formats, and priorities to better **serve the needs** of the communities it informs.

Reflective practice may not always be easy or economically feasible. Many newsrooms lack the time and resources to **systematically analyse** their work. But that doesn't mean it's not possible or valuable.

Journalists' associations, press councils, journalism schools, and European initiatives can help **create spaces and tools** for reflection, exchange, and peer learning. Promoting these moments of collective review is not a luxury: it is part of building more responsive, resilient, and trustworthy journalism.

Giving also positive messages

Journalism has long focused on what goes wrong, bad news, disasters, and failures. This emphasis is **deeply rooted** in the profession's role as a watchdog. However, in recent years, several studies have shown that audiences are not only sensitive to constant negativity. They also want **coverage that includes progress**, solutions, and hope.

After a crisis, stories about **wrongdoing and accountability** remain crucial. But so are those that highlight **new strategies, policy shifts**, innova-

tions, or **community responses** aimed at preventing future risks. These are not soft or secondary topics: they are central to understanding how societies learn, adapt, and rebuild.

Some media organisations have clearly embraced the idea that journalism does not just report on the world. It also helps shape it. Reporting on potential and innovation, when done rigorously and critically, can help **best practices** spread, inspire public debate, and show how change is possible. It's a powerful way for journalism to have a real-world impact.

This is the thinking behind two emerging approaches: **constructive journalism** and **solutions journalism**.

Constructive journalism aims to provide a **more balanced and accurate view** of the world by **avoiding the overrepresentation** of negative news. It doesn't sugarcoat reality, but instead reframes stories to include context, progress, and possible paths forward. The goal is not to offer feel-good content, but to **tell the whole story**.

Solutions journalism takes this **a step further**. It focuses specifically on **responses** to pressing social, environmental, and technological problems. It investigates what works, under what conditions, and why. Solutions stories are **evidence-based** and transparent about their limitations: they show that one answer may not fit all, but some responses make a difference and can be adapted elsewhere.

Highlighting successful interventions, whether public policies, grassroots initiatives, or scientific innovations, not only informs **better decision-making**, but also supports **recovery efforts** and prepares societies for future challenges. Perhaps most importantly, it helps **counter the widespread sense of helplessness** that can follow a crisis.

Journalism that recognises **people's agency**, their capacity to act, adapt, and build, is not only more accurate, but more **empowering**. This shift in perspective is still gaining ground, but its potential for strengthening public resilience and democratic engagement is already clear.

06

How to find help at the European Competence Centre for Science Communication

The European Competence Centre for Science Communication is an online platform, connected to a network of national and regional hubs – the COALESCE Hubs, offering resources, services and training to improve science communication programmes and projects in all domains and contexts.

In the platform, you can find a matchmaking tool to connect with experts and organisations, a scicomm toolbox with quality-validated science communication resources, curated science communication collections on varied topics, a connection with the ENJOI Observatory – looking at the European media landscape with a focus on science journalism –, among others.

Visit scicommcentre.eu

Further reading:

This friendly guide is a friendly version from the “Guidelines for non science journalists in times of crisis”.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14016521>

The Crisis Navigator is an interactive guide to support science communication professionals to better imagine and anticipate challenges, based on the guiding question: How to contribute when a crisis emerges?

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11446975>

Strategies to address critical challenges to effective science–society relations, including misinformation and trust approaches.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14826013>

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